

1 **Effect of the differences in spectral response of Mediterranean tree**
2 **canopies on the estimation of evapotranspiration using vegetation**
3 **index-based crop coefficients**

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1 **Abstract**

2 The vegetation index (VI)-reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) method incorporates the
3 estimation of basal crop coefficients from spectral VIs into the FAO56 guidelines for
4 computing crop evapotranspiration. Previous research pointed to the possibility of the
5 differential spectral response of some Mediterranean crops, specifically olive trees. To
6 evaluate this hypothesis and the potential related effects on the VI-ET_o method, this
7 work studied the spectral response of four Mediterranean canopies under full vegetation
8 coverage: three fruit trees (olive, orange and almond trees), and the holm oak trees of
9 the *dehesas* ecosystem. Spectral measurements were taken on dense vegetation placed
10 on a workbench and over dense treetops, avoiding in both cases the effect of soil
11 background. The results showed that the soil adjusted vegetation index (SAVI) for full-
12 cover olive trees was significantly lower than for other fruit trees (0.57 for olive trees
13 vs. 0.71 for orange tree and 0.70 for almond tree). SAVI of olive vegetation measured
14 on the workbench was lower than that measured over treetops, probably due to the
15 effects of canopy architecture and shadowing. SAVI obtained on oak treetops (0.51)
16 was even lower than that on olive treetops. The differential response of olive and oak
17 trees showed notable effects on the computation of ET (and water stress) by using ET
18 measurements with the eddy covariance method. In the olive orchards, RMSD was
19 reduced from 0.73 to 0.6 mm day⁻¹ when daily ET was estimated assuming SAVI_{max} =
20 0.57 in comparison with a generic value for Mediterranean crops. Moreover, the
21 quantification of soil water deficit in the *dehesa* was different whether the generic or
22 specific value was used, with a difference in average water stress coefficient of 0.28,
23 higher in the first scenario.

24 **Keywords:** vegetation indices; full vegetation coverage; evapotranspiration; crop
25 coefficients; VI-ET_o method; Mediterranean tree canopies.

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Vegetation indices (VIs) characterize vegetation canopies quantitatively from spectral
3 information recorded by satellite, airborne sensors, or field spectroradiometers. They are
4 well correlated with certain vegetation biophysical properties and parameters, such as
5 leaf area index, ground cover fraction, emissivity, albedo, or the fraction of
6 photosynthetically active radiation absorbed by the canopy (Asrar et al., 1985;
7 Choudhury et al., 1994; Carlson and Ripley, 1997; Glenn et al., 2008). This makes VIs
8 useful in monitoring processes related to photosynthesis or transpiration (Glenn et al.,
9 2008). The normalized difference vegetation index, NDVI (Rouse et al., 1974), was one
10 of the first VIs proposed, and it is the one most commonly used as a canopy descriptor
11 together with the soil adjusted vegetation index (SAVI; Huete et al., 1988), which
12 minimizes the soil-background influences on the canopy reflectance.

13 One of the most widespread approaches to estimate water consumption over agricultural
14 areas using remote sensing is the calculation of a water balance in the crop root zone,
15 including a VI as a crop growth descriptor. The VI-reference evapotranspiration (ET_0)
16 method consists of the application of the FAO56 guidelines for computing crop water
17 requirements (Allen et al., 1998; 2005) with crop coefficients derived from VIs.
18 Applications of this approach have been presented by Neale et al. (1996), Jayanthi et al.
19 (2001), Calera et al. (2005), Er-Raki et al. (2007), González-Dugo et al. (2008); and
20 reviewed by Glenn et al. (2011) and Calera et al. (2017).

21 The crop coefficients can be expressed in a single or dual formulation, depending on
22 whether the crop transpiration and soil evaporation are integrated into a single
23 coefficient (K_c), or if both terms are expressed separately, with crop transpiration
24 represented by the basal crop coefficient (K_{cb}). Some authors have indicated the NDVI-

1 K_{cb} relationship to be linear for herbaceous crops such as corn and wheat (Baush and
2 Neale, 1987; Neale et al., 1989; Duchemin et al., 2006), or vineyards (Campos et al.,
3 2010). Due to the overestimation of the basal crop coefficient for incomplete vegetation
4 covers on dark soils, Bausch (1993, 1995) suggested computing K_{cb} from SAVI,
5 expanding the applicability of the method to a wider range of soil reflectance values.

6 Numerous VI- K_{cb} empirical relationships can be found in the literature for different
7 crops, such as cotton and sugarbeet (Neale et al., 1996; Hunsaker et al., 2003; González-
8 Dugo et al., 2008), potato (Jayanthi et al., 2007), wheat (Hunsaker et al., 2005a), corn
9 (González-Piqueras et al., 2004), vineyards (Consoli and Barbagallo, 2012) or apple
10 orchards (Odi-Lara et al., 2016). González-Dugo et al. (2009) proposed a generalized
11 linear equation to calculate K_{cb} from SAVI, initially developed over maize and soybean
12 fields in Iowa, but later applied in Mediterranean semi-arid regions (Padilla et al., 2011;
13 González-Dugo et al., 2013; Mateos et al., 2013; Consoli and Vanella, 2014; Carpintero
14 et al., 2018; Jódar et al., 2018).

15 This generalized equation was validated in irrigated areas with annual crops (corn,
16 wheat, cotton, and garlic) and fruit tree crops (mandarin, olive, and peach) in the
17 Guadalquivir river basin in Southern Spain (Padilla et al., 2011; Mateos et al., 2013).

18 Although this validation with *in-situ* ET measurements produced satisfactory results for
19 most crops, some inaccuracy observed by Mateos et al. (2013) for olive orchards
20 induced these authors to hypothesise that SAVI of pure olive tree vegetation (one of the
21 parameters used by the model) might be less than for other canopies, due to particular
22 reflectance properties of this species.

23 VIs for full vegetation coverage have been determined for some annual crops, showing
24 similar values over wheat, cotton and sugarbeet with NDVI of between 0.90 and 0.93
25 (Hunsaker et al., 2003; Hunsaker et al., 2005a; Duchemin et al., 2006; González-Dugo

1 et al., 2008) and SAVI between 0.7 and 0.75 (González-Dugo et al., 2008; Padilla et al.,
2 2011). A value of SAVI equal to 0.78 was measured over full-cover potato vegetation
3 (Jayanthi et al., 2007). These values were slightly higher than those observed for corn,
4 with NDVI of between 0.81 and 0.87 (Neale et al., 1989; Bausch et al., 1993; González-
5 Piqueras et al., 2004) and SAVI of 0.65 (Padilla et al., 2011). To our knowledge, VIs for
6 full-cover tree crops have not been reported.

7 Other Mediterranean tree species with similar morphological characteristics to those of
8 olive trees could also have a spectral response akin to that of olive trees. One such
9 species could be the holm oak tree (*Quercus Ilex* L.), the main tree species in the most
10 characteristic agroforestry system in central and southern Spain, the oak savanna
11 (grassland, shrubs, and widely scattered oak trees), locally known as *dehesa*. This
12 system, that occupies more than 3 million ha in the Iberian Peninsula (Moreno and
13 Pulido, 2008), presents many similarities with Mediterranean tree crops, like their
14 adaptation to water deficit, developing similar responses to increase their tolerance to
15 water stress. Both species have thick leaves with relatively small stomata,
16 (characteristics that favor high water use efficient) and extensive root systems to extract
17 water in a large soil volume during the dry season (Moreno et al., 2005; Santos et al.,
18 2007). While olive trees are the main crop in the irrigated agricultural systems in the
19 Guadalquivir Basin, a great part of the upper basin is occupied by *dehesas*, covering the
20 catchments of the main surface reservoirs and aquifers that store water for irrigation in
21 the basin.

22 The aim of this work was to investigate the possible spectral response difference of four
23 representative Mediterranean tree species (olive, orange, almond and oak trees) to
24 evaluate the effect of this difference on the estimation of evapotranspiration using
25 vegetation index-based crop coefficients.

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2 **2. Material and methods**

3 *2.1. Experimental sites and field radiometry*

4 This study was conducted on four experimental sites within the Guadalquivir river basin
5 (Fig. 1). The Guadalquivir river basin is located in southern Spain (Fig. 1), has a typical
6 Mediterranean climate and holds about 900,000 thousand ha of irrigated agriculture.
7 Table 1 shows the main characteristics of each site, including the canopy type, location,
8 and the purpose of this research. Site A was a commercial farm (*Mingaobe* farm) where
9 one olive orchard and one orange orchard, both equipped with a drip irrigation system,
10 were selected. Site B consisted of small experimental orchards of olive, orange and
11 almond trees located at the experimental farm *Alameda del Obispo*, in Cordoba. Site C
12 consisted of a three-year-old olive orchard, also on the experimental farm *Alameda del*
13 *Obispo* and equipped with a drip irrigation system. Site D was a *dehesa* in *Santa*
14 *Clotilde* farm (*Sierra de Cardeña and Montoro* Natural Park).

15 Ground radiometric measurements were performed using an ASD Spectroradiometer
16 (model FieldSpec 3, ASD Inc., Boulder, CO, USA). This instrument provides uniform
17 VIS/NIR/SWIR data collection with a spectral range from 350 nm to 2500 nm (the
18 sampling interval is 1.4 nm from 350 to 1050 nm, and 2 nm from 1000 to 2500 nm).
19 Spectral measurements were taken using a 1.5 m optic fibre cable with a field of view
20 (FOV) of 25°, and referenced with regular measurements over a white Spectralon panel
21 (Labsphere, North Sutton, NH) with 100 % reflectance across the entire spectrum.
22 The canopy reflectance information was integrated into the Landsat 7 Enhanced
23 Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+) and Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) sensors
24 bandwidths using the spectral response function of each instrument for those

1 wavelengths. Data in the red and NIR regions, required for computing the VIs, were
2 estimated by averaging the reflectance values corresponding to bands 3 (0.63-0.69 μm)
3 and 4 (0.78-0.90 μm) in ETM+ respectively, and bands 4 (0.64-0.67 μm) and 5 (0.85-
4 0.88 μm) in OLI sensor, respectively. The NDVI and SAVI vegetation indices were
5 calculated as follows:

$$6 \quad NDVI = \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{\text{red}}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{\text{red}}} \quad (1)$$

$$7 \quad SAVI = \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{\text{red}}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{\text{red}} + L} (1 + L) \quad (2)$$

8 where ρ_{NIR} and ρ_{red} are the reflectance in the red and NIR regions of the electromagnetic
9 spectrum, respectively, and L is a soil normalization factor, generally taken to be 0.5
10 (Huete, 1988).

11 Spectral measurements were taken over dense, fresh vegetation placed on a workbench
12 and over dense treetops on experimental sites A, B and D. The intention in both cases
13 was to avoid soil background effects on the determination of pure vegetation indices.

14 Freshly cut orange and olive tree branches were arranged in a 20-cm thick vegetation
15 layer on each of two workbenches of dimensions 1 m \times 1.95 m, mimicking full ground
16 cover. The ASD sensor was placed 0.4 m above the layer of branches, resulting in a
17 FOV diameter of 0.18 m. Measurements were taken on day-of-year (DoY) 254, 2013, at
18 solar elevation angles of 45°, 52.7° (coinciding with the Landsat-8 overpass time; 10:58
19 UTC) and 57° (daily maximum solar elevation angle). At each measuring time, three
20 replications were measured at each of four sampling points on each of the two
21 workbenches.

22 Spectral measurements on the treetops in the experimental site A were acquired on
23 DoYs 114, 126 and 142 of 2013 over 6 olive and 6 orange trees (3 replications per

1 treetop) ensuring full vegetation ground cover in the measurements FOV. The sensor
2 was placed 0.4 m above the treetops with the help of a portable ladder. Measuring time
3 was selected to coincide with Landsat-7 overpass time (at 10:52 UTC), so that the solar
4 elevation angles changed depending on the date of the year (ranging from 58.3° to
5 64.6°).

6 Radiometric measurements in experimental site B were collected over the olive, orange
7 and almond trees with the densest vegetation ground cover within the experimental plot
8 on three different dates. Measurements were taken at 1 m height above the top of the
9 canopy with the help of a lifting platform. Four sampling points per tree were selected
10 and three replicates were measured at each point. On the first date (DoY 222, 2016),
11 data were collected at solar elevation angles of 45° and 61°, the latter coinciding with
12 Landsat-8 overpass time. The second date was programmed on DoY 16, 2017, with the
13 aim of having spectral data in the winter, with low solar elevation: angles of 27.5°
14 (Landsat-8 overpass time) and 31.05° (daily maximum solar elevation). Almond trees
15 were excluded from winter measurements because they do not have leaves in winter. On
16 the last measuring date (DoY 166, 2018), the measurements were performed at solar
17 elevation angles of 45° and 67° (Landsat-8 overpass time).

18 In Site D (Santa Clotilde *dehesa*), spectral data were acquired over young oak treetops
19 distributed throughout the farm (10 measurements each day). The selection of young
20 trees was to facilitate the measurement since mature trees are too high. Measurements
21 were performed on ten dates (DoY 188 and 239, 2015; DoY 139, 175, 231, 265, 285
22 and 348, 2016; DoY 129 and 193, 2017) coinciding with Landsat 8 overpass times, so
23 that the solar elevation angle varied throughout the measurement dates.

24 *2.2. Vegetation index-derived crop coefficients for estimating evapotranspiration*

1 The FAO methodology for computing crop evapotranspiration consists of multiplying a
 2 reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) by a crop coefficient (Doorenbos and Pruitt, 1977;
 3 Allen et al., 1998):

$$4 \quad ET = K_c ET_o \quad (3)$$

5 The FAO56 crop coefficient dual approach distinguishes between crop transpiration and
 6 soil surface evaporation (Allen et al., 1998):

$$7 \quad K_c = K_{cb} K_s + K_e \quad (4)$$

8 where K_{cb} is the basal crop/canopy coefficient and determines the vegetation
 9 transpiration, K_s is the water stress coefficient that quantifies the reduction in
 10 transpiration due to soil water deficit, and K_e is the soil evaporation coefficient.

11 K_{cb} can be derived from SAVI using the linear relationship proposed by González-Dugo
 12 et al. (2009):

$$13 \quad K_{cb} = \frac{K_{cbfull}}{f_{cmax}} \left(\frac{SAVI - SAVI_{min}}{SAVI_{max} - SAVI_{min}} \right) \text{ if } f_c < f_{cmax} \quad (5a)$$

$$14 \quad K_{cb} = K_{cbfull} \text{ if } f_c \geq f_{cmax} \quad (5b)$$

15 where the subscripts max and min refer to the values of SAVI for full canopy ground
 16 cover and bare soil, respectively, f_{cmax} is the ground cover fraction (f_c) at which K_{cb}
 17 reaches its maximum value (K_{cbfull}). Note that in Eq. 5 f_c is assumed to be:

$$18 \quad f_c = \frac{SAVI - SAVI_{min}}{SAVI_{max} - SAVI_{min}} \quad (6)$$

19

20 *2.3. Evaluation of the effect of crop spectral response*

1 The effect of the differences in spectral response on the estimation of evapotranspiration
2 using vegetation index-based crop coefficients was evaluated in Sites C and D.

3 The application of Eqs. 3-5 to the young olive orchard in Site C, reported in Mateos et
4 al. (2013), was re-evaluated modifying $SAVI_{max}$ according to the radiometric
5 measurements results taken in experimental sites A and B. The evaluation used both,
6 daily ET data measured with the eddy covariance method (details about these
7 measurements are in Testi et al., 2004) and a series of 5 Landsat-7 images acquired
8 during 2000 (Table 2) used to obtain SAVI to compute K_{cb} (details in Mateos et al.,
9 2013).

10 In Site D, the evaluation consisted of computing daily K_c in Eq. 3 from on-site
11 measurements of ET and ET_o . Reference ET was obtained from a nearby weather
12 station (belonging to the Spanish Meteorology Agency and located at 3 km from the
13 site) and ET was measured with the eddy covariance method. Once K_c values were
14 determined, Eq. 4 was solved for K_s , which was computed, entering K_{cb} calculated with
15 Eq. 5 using SAVI obtained from a series of satellite images (Table 2) and interpolated
16 on a daily time-step, and $SAVI_{max}$ resulting from radiometric measurements. $SAVI_{min}$
17 was assumed to be 0.09 for bare soil, derived from field measurements taken by
18 González-Dugo et al. (2008), and $K_{cb full} = 0.65$ for $f_{c max} = 0.6$. Stoner and Baumgardner
19 (1981) identified some spectral curves of the observed soil reflectance according to
20 differences in moisture content, mineralogy or particle size, and Jackson et al. (1991)
21 obtained a NDVI value of 0.1 for bar soil. The assessment was conducted during the
22 summer, when only the oak trees are green, the understorey herbaceous layer is
23 completely dry, and K_e in Eq. 4 is zero because of the absence of rainfall.

24 The eddy covariance equipment in Site D consisted of a 3D sonic anemometer (model
25 CSAT3 Campbell Scientific Inc.) measuring horizontal and vertical fluctuations of

1 temperature and wind speed, and a hygrometer (model KH20, Campbell Scientific Inc.)
2 to estimate water vapour fluctuations. The equipment was installed 17.5 m above the
3 ground, over the combined holm oak and grassland system. At the beginning of 2015,
4 the hygrometer was replaced by an open Path CO₂/H₂O Gas Analyzer LICOR-7500,
5 taking simultaneous measurements of carbon dioxide and water vapour in turbulent air
6 structures. These measurements were recorded with a frequency of 10 Hz, and half-
7 hourly averages were computed. Turbulent flux measurements were corrected for
8 density effects due to heat and water vapour transfer (Webb et al., 1980). The net
9 radiation was firstly obtained with a net radiometer (model NR-Lite, Kipp&Zonen) and
10 from 2015 with a four-component net-radiometer (model NR01, Hukseflux Thermal
11 Sensors). The relative humidity and air temperature (model HMP155, Vaisala) were
12 also measured. The soil heat flux was determined by using soil heat flux plates (model
13 HFP01, Hukseflux Thermal Sensors), together with soil thermocouples to calculate
14 temporal variation of the temperature above the soil plates. These data were corrected
15 with the soil moisture obtained with five humidity soil probes (model EnviroSCAN,
16 Sentek Pty. Ltd.), taking measurements continuously at depths of 10, 30 and 50 cm. The
17 quality of the measurements was tested by Andreu et al. (2018a, b) for 2012 summer
18 season, resulting in an average closure of 86%. For the period 2014-2015, the closure
19 balance was of 91 %. The energy balance closure method used preserves the Bowen
20 ratio, and the corrector factor is subsequently estimated on a daily basis (Mauder et al.,
21 2018).

22 SAVI in Site D was obtained from a set of 11 images from Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2A
23 (Table 2). The Landsat images have 30 m spatial resolution in the visible and NIR
24 spectral bands, and it is of 10 m for those provided by Sentinel-2A (subsequently
25 resampled at 30m for the analysis). The Landsat surface reflectance climate data record

1 (SR CDR) (<http://espa.cr.usgs.gov>) provided geometrically- and atmospherically-
2 corrected data that was used to estimate SAVI from Landsat-8 images. Georeferenced
3 surface reflectance from Sentinel-2A was generated with the Sen2cor processor, which
4 performs the atmospheric, terrain and cirrus correction of Top-Of-Atmosphere input
5 data (Mueller-Wilm et al, 2016). In addition, the data fusion technique STARFM (Gao
6 et al., 2006) was applied on two dates to fill a long period without cloudless images.
7 This approach compares one pair of observed Landsat/MODIS images acquired on the
8 same day to predict maps on the Landsat spatial scale on other MODIS observation
9 dates. SAVI used to compute K_{cb} for Site D was the result of averaging SAVI across an
10 area composed of nine $30\text{ m} \times 30\text{ m}$ pixels, coinciding with the coordinates of the
11 ground ET measurements (Table 2).

12

13 **3. Results and discussion**

14 *3.1. Spectral response of Mediterranean fruit and oak trees*

15 Table 3 shows mean SAVI and NDVI for the fruit and oak trees vegetation averaged
16 over all observation dates and times, and measured over the workbench and the treetop.
17 Both SAVI and NDVI were significantly lower for olive than for orange tree vegetation
18 (Tukey's HSD –honestly significant difference– test, confidence level of 0.95). The
19 difference was greater when determined over the workbench than over the treetop.
20 SAVI measured over olive treetop (0.57) was also lower than over almond (0.70),
21 which was similar to SAVI over orange treetop (0.71). Average SAVI over the oak
22 treetop (0.51) was even lower than over the olive treetop. The difference between
23 species of treetop NDVI was less than the difference of treetop SAVI. NDVI over
24 almond treetop (0.83) was between the values determined for olive and orange treetops

1 (0.80 and 0.87 respectively), while NDVI over oak treetop was less than over any of the
2 other three species.

3 The difference between SAVI and NDVI measured over olive vegetation on the
4 workbench and the treetop was likely due to the effect of canopy architecture and
5 shadowing. Jackson et al. (1991) demonstrated how canopy architecture determines the
6 directions of radiation reflection, with effects on VI. Norman et al. (1985) analysed the
7 impact of leaf-angle distribution on the canopy reflectance, and found how shadows
8 within the canopy hit by the foliage that were illuminated by the sun, and therefore, the
9 reflectance tended to be highest here. Fig. 2 shows zenithal photographs extended over
10 the field of view of the spectroradiometer at the measuring time on the workbench and
11 the treetops. Olive and orange tree vegetation on the workbench was visually more
12 homogeneous than on the treetop, shadows were less apparent, and both the upper- and
13 under-sides of leaves were exposed. However, it is of interest that the difference in
14 indices of olive tree vegetation obtained over workbench vs. treetop was not observed
15 when determined over orange tree vegetation (SAVI of 0.72 and 0.71, and NDVI of
16 0.90 and 0.87 on the workbench and the treetops, respectively). This discrepancy
17 between species occurred for both SAVI and NDVI, contradicting Zhang et al. (2015),
18 who found that SAVI was greater in shaded than in sunlit leaves while NDVI was
19 hardly affected by shadows. Conversely, our measurements over olive tree vegetation
20 on the workbench (with limited shadow effects) yielded lower values of both indices
21 than the measurements over the olive treetop (with shadows visually evident); while the
22 measurements over orange tree vegetation yielded values of SAVI and NDVI that were
23 similar on both the workbench and the treetops (Table 3).

24 The suspicion of the little or non-effect of the solar elevation angle derived from the
25 zenithal photographs in Fig. 2 was corroborated by spectroradiometer measurements

1 (Fig. 3). Average SAVI and NDVI remained stable in the range of solar elevation angle
2 27°-67° for all canopies. The deviations from the horizontal line (indicating the overall
3 mean index value) for olive and orange tree vegetation were explained by the measuring
4 setup (workbench vs. treetop) rather than the solar elevation angle. These results
5 supported the normalizing feature of both vegetation indices and their robustness in
6 detecting vegetation properties under different solar elevation angles and full ground
7 cover. Solar angle effects on VIs have been discussed in the literature (Pinter et al,
8 1987; 1990; Jackson et al., 1979). Some works found differences in VIs values during
9 the middle growth stage of the canopy with changing solar angles, although this
10 sensitivity was nearly absent when vegetation cover was high (Jackson et al., 1991;
11 Ishihara et al., 2015; Ma et al., 2019).

12 The results also support the hypothesis of Mateos et al. (2013), who conjectured that the
13 $SAVI_{max}$ for olive trees could be different to that assumed for other Mediterranean field
14 and woody crops for estimating basal crop coefficients. Moreover, the spectral response
15 of oak trees, another typical Mediterranean tree, was similar to that of the olive trees.
16 SAVI over orange and almond treetops was close to $SAVI_{max} = 0.75$ assumed by Mateos
17 et al. (2013) for the estimation of the basal crop coefficient of Mediterranean field and
18 woody crops. Since treetop measurements represent field conditions better than
19 workbench ones, we recommend using $SAVI_{max}$ equal to 0.57 and 0.71 for olive and
20 orange orchards, respectively. In addition, a $SAVI_{max}$ value of 0.51 is recommended for
21 oak trees.

22

23 *3.2. Effect of tree canopy spectral response on the estimation of water consumption*
24 *from VIs- derived crop coefficients*

1 Mateos et al. (2013) estimated daily ET of a young olive orchard (Site C) applying the
2 VI-ET_o method assuming SAVI_{max} = 0.75, that was compared with eddy covariance
3 measurements published in Testi et al. (2004). Figure 4a reproduces Fig. 9b in Mateos
4 et al. (2013) showing measured and simulated ET throughout the 2000 irrigation season,
5 with root mean square deviation (RMSD) of the estimations equal to 0.73 mm day⁻¹.
6 Fig. 4b shows the same measured ET data and new estimates of ET assuming SAVI_{max}
7 = 0.57. The new estimates of ET were closer to the ET measured than the estimates in
8 Mateos et al. (2013), and RMSD was reduced to 0.6 mm day⁻¹. The improvement was
9 especially noticeable in the months of May to July. These results suggest that the
10 particular reflectance properties of olive trees have an impact on the estimations of ET
11 by the VI-ET_o method, a value of SAVI_{max} of 0.57 being more appropriate than 0.75.

12 The soil water deficit in the *dehesa* (Site D) was estimated during the dry season (July
13 to mid-September) of 2014 and 2015, when the oak trees were the only green and
14 transpiring vegetation on the ground. Soil evaporation was assumed to be negligible
15 ($K_e = 0$), because there was no rainfall during the calculation period, which started 40
16 days after the last rainfall event in 2014 and 15 days after a 14 mm rainfall. Fig. 5
17 presents daily and 10-day average ET_o, measured ET and computed K_s for the two
18 summer seasons and assuming SAVI_{max} = 0.75 or SAVI_{max} = 0.51. Measured ET
19 decreased progressively in both years due to the decreasing trend of ET_o and the
20 increase in water deficit. ET fell to approximately 0.5 mm day⁻¹ at the end of the
21 summer, a rate similar to the 0.7 mm day⁻¹ measured by David et al. (2007) in a similar
22 environment in Portugal. The important issue here was that the quantification of water
23 stress by means of K_s was very different assuming SAVI_{max} = 0.75 or SAVI_{max} = 0.51. K_s
24 is equal to one in the absence of water deficit and it decreases to zero when the trees
25 stop transpiring. Average K_s during the 2014 summer period were of 0.76 and 0.48

1 assuming $SAVI_{max} = 0.75$ or $SAVI_{max} = 0.51$, respectively. Respective minimum K_s (in
2 early September) were 0.59 and 0.38. In 2015, the results were similar to those of 2014:
3 average K_s of 0.80 and 0.51 for $SAVI_{max} = 0.75$ and $SAVI_{max} = 0.51$, respectively, and
4 minimum K_s of 0.68 and 0.43. The overall difference of 0.28 in K_s meant a considerably
5 different estimation of water stress, depending on the value of $SAVI_{max}$ selected for the
6 application of the VI- ET_o method, underlining the importance of considering the
7 particular spectral response of oak trees for computing water balances and estimating
8 water deficit in *dehesa* systems.

9

10 **4. Conclusions**

11 The results of this research revealed substantial differences between the spectral
12 responses of the Mediterranean trees studied: olive and holm oak trees on one hand, and
13 orange and almond trees on the other. The SAVI of full vegetation of olive and oak
14 trees was significantly lower than the SAVI of full vegetation of the other two fruit
15 trees. The SAVI of olive tree vegetation placed on a workbench was less than when
16 measured over treetops that was likely due to canopy architecture and shadow effects.
17 Both SAVI and NDVI were insensitive to the solar elevation angle. The results
18 supported the robustness of these two VIs for estimating basal crop coefficients, and
19 corroborated the hypothesis of Mateos et al. (2013) who pointed out that olive trees
20 could have particular spectral properties compared to other Mediterranean crops.
21 Orange and almond trees behaved similarly to what Mateos et al. 2013 and Gonzalez-
22 Dugo et al. (2013) reported for the whole range of Mediterranean crops. The implication
23 of the differential response of olive trees for the computation of ET using the VI- ET_o
24 method was notable, as was demonstrated in comparing ET data collected in a young

1 olive orchard. The spectral response of holm oaks in the *dehesa* ecosystem was similar
2 to that of the olive trees. Holm oaks and olive trees share some morphological features
3 and the adaptation to dry periods characteristic of Mediterranean climate. Measurements
4 of ET with the eddy covariance method allowed the estimation of the degree of water
5 stress of oak trees in the *dehesa* system applying the VI-ET_o method, resulting in a
6 considerable underestimation of water stress level with the generic SAVI_{max} value.

7 The assessment highlighted the importance of taking into account the specific spectral
8 response of this species (the specific SAVI_{max}) in ET and water stress monitoring
9 applications, when VIs-based remote sensed techniques are used. It is recommended to
10 take SAVI_{max} equal to 0.57 for olive trees, 0.51 for oak trees, and 0.71 for orange and
11 almond trees and the rest of Mediterranean crops as long as there is no different
12 information. The use of appropriate values could have a significant impact on irrigation
13 recommendations to farmers in olive groves, as well as on the accurate modelling of
14 hydrological processes of *dehesa* landscape, essential on the ecosystem decision-making
15 and management planning.

16

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2 Figure 1: Location of the Guadalquivir river basin and experimental sites.

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2 Figure 2: Photographs extended over the field of view of the ASD spectroradiometer at
 3 the measuring time (at two solar elevation angles) on the workbench and the treetop
 4 over olive, orange and almond tree vegetation of experimental site B.

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2 Figure 3: Relationship between the SAVI and NDVI values measured and the solar
 3 elevation angles for (a) olive, (b) orange, (c) almond, and (d) young oak trees in the
 4 experimental sites A, B and D, under maximum vegetation coverage conditions.

a)

b)

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2 Figure 4: Daily temporal evolution of modeled (line) and measured (triangles) ET over
 3 the olive orchard (site C) by applying the VI-ET₀ method with a maximum SAVI value
 4 of 0.75 (Figure 4a) and 0.57 (Figure 4b).

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3 Figure 5: Evolution of daily and 10-day average values of K_s under two scenarios
4 ($SAVI_{max} = 0.75$ and $SAVI_{max} = 0.51$) during the dry season (July to mid-September) of
5 (a) 2014 and (b) 2015. The daily and 10-day average ET and ET_o measured are also
6 included.

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2 | Figure 5: Evolution of 10-day average values of K_s under two scenarios ($SAVI_{max} = 0.75$
 3 and $SAVI_{max} = 0.51$) during the dry season (July to mid-September) of (a) 2014 and (b)
 4 2015. The 10-day average ET and ET_0 measured are also included.

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8 Table 1: Main characteristics of the experimental sites.

Site	Canopy type	Area (ha)	Lat/Long	a.s.l. (m)	Purpose
A	Olive trees (<i>Olea europaea</i> L.) 5.5 x 7m spacing	11.67	37°46'55.2''N	83	Field radiometry
	Orange trees (<i>Citrus x sinensis</i> L.) 4 x 6m spacing	20.12	5°4'36'' W		
B	Olive trees (<i>Olea europaea</i> L.)	0.6	37°51'33.7''N	92	Field radiometry
	Orange trees (<i>Citrus x sinensis</i> L.)	0.1	4°47'44.5'' W		
	Almond trees (<i>Prunus dulcis</i>)	0.1			
C	Olive trees (<i>Olea europaea</i> L.) 3.5 x 7m spacing	4	37°51'13.8''N 4°48'29'' W	95	Water balance modelling
D	<i>Dehesa</i> : oak trees (<i>Quercus Ilex</i> L.)	292	38°12'36.6''N 4°17'14.9''W	740	Field radiometry Water balance modelling

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14 Table 2: Acquisition dates of images of Landsat-7 and 8, Sentinel-2A and STARFM,

15 scene number and SAVI average value for each canopy.

<i>Date</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Scene</i>	<i>Canopy</i>	<i>SAVI</i>
02-05-00	L7(ETM+)	201-34	Olive	0.20
18-05-00	L7(ETM+)	201-34	Olive	0.19
21-07-00	L7(ETM+)	201-34	Olive	0.18
20-08-00	L7(ETM+)	201-34	Olive	0.19
07-09-00	L7(ETM+)	201-34	Olive	0.20
30-06-14	STARFM ^a	201-33	Holm oak	0.26
20-07-14	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.23
05-08-14	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.23
21-08-14	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.22
06-09-14	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.23
08-10-14	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.28
21-06-15	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.25
07-07-15	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.24
23-07-15	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.24
01-08-15	Sentinel-2A		Holm oak	0.22
28-08-15	Sentinel-2A		Holm oak	0.22
25-09-15	L8(OLI)	201-33	Holm oak	0.20

1 ^aReflectance images generated by the data fusion technique STARFM (Gao et al., 2006) using
2 the Landsat-8 and MODIS (product MOD09GQ) satellites

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11 Table 3: SAVI and NDVI average values measured over the fruit crops and oak trees
12 with full ground cover situations. The results of the Tukey’s HSD comparison statistical
13 test (applied to each column) are included.

Workbench		Treetop	
SAVI	NDVI	SAVI	NDVI

Olive tree	0.49 _b	0.67 _b	0.57 _b	0.80 _b
Orange tree	0.72 _a	0.90 _a	0.71 _a	0.87 _a
Almond tree			0.70 _a	0.83 _b
Oak tree			0.51 _c	0.76 _c

1 ***a, b** and **c** are the groups in which the means are not significantly different from one another